

Advancing Health Equity through Community-engaged Research

The RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) asked members of the RADx-UP consortium how we can expand the community-engaged work of the RADx-UP program to address health disparities research in the U.S. beyond the COVID-19 pandemic.

More than 100 members of the consortium shared valuable insights and experiences that inform the following strategic directions and themes.

Direction A.

Disrupt the research paradigm to ensure that the communities most impacted are able to drive the research

Goal

We will work to upend the research paradigm to ensure that the community is a trusted and equal partner at every point of the research process.

Why

Community-engaged research is often conducted with the intention of including community representation in the process, but power remains with the researchers as the ones asking the questions, analyzing the meaning of data, and disseminating findings.

How

A1. Develop inclusive, trustworthy research teams that center the perspectives of communities

Our strategy is to ensure that research teams include community members with a range of experiences, and that community voices influence and steer the research cycle. We intend to demonstrate our trustworthiness and will develop stronger solutions through better representation of the communities with whom we partner for research.

A2. Redesign the research ecosystem to shift resources, process and power toward communities

Our strategy is to create a new paradigm for research development. This includes embracing flexible, action oriented approaches that respect the expertise of the communities impacted by health inequities.

A3: Change the rules and incentives of academia to reward and value community-based research

The current models for professional advancement as an academic researcher seldom incentivize community driven research. Our strategy is to invest in, and advocate for, academic rewards that encourage and value community partnerships and community-based research activities.

Direction B.

Develop a sustainable, accessible, research-ready infrastructure to enable rapid response to emerging needs

Goal

We will build relationships of mutual understanding between communities and academic researchers before the need for research arises.

We will establish integrated data systems, refine our approaches to sharing results, and invest in research supports (e.g., staff, systems, and training) that last beyond single projects.

Why

The research ecosystem must support the ability of community members and researchers to immediately and effectively collaborate, lead, and participate in research whenever it is needed.

How

B4: Create and institutionalize opportunities for bidirectional learning, co-learning, and connection between academic researchers and community members

Our strategy is to intentionally create meaningful, equitable relationships between academic researchers and community members. We seek to build trust and facilitate understanding of each other's needs in order to enable more effective responses to the next research opportunities. This work must include intentionally building a stronger pipeline for new talent in the field of research.

B5: Create a transparent, accessible and compatible data system, and invest in training and infrastructure to ensure its sustainability

Our strategy is to develop standards and systems that ensure integrated and accessible data across research projects. We will build capacity around data systems at the community level through investments in infrastructure, staff, tools, and training.

B6: Support knowledge sharing in a way that is clear, accessible, and actionable for communities

Our strategy is to create a more robust system for disseminating research findings throughout communities in meaningful ways. This means shifting expectations for how findings are documented and shared, to include immediately usable information and more diversified outlets.

B7: Fund and improve sustained infrastructure to support the longevity of community-driven research

Our strategy is to invest in staffing, training, communication tools, data systems, and other key research supports that will last beyond single research projects. Because this infrastructure will not have to be rebuilt with each new effort, we can build on prior learnings and respond to emerging research opportunities more quickly.

Direction C.

Leverage RADx UP influence to cultivate funding mechanisms (within and beyond NIH) that respect community needs and voices

Goal

We will encourage grants with realistic timeframes and adequate funds to enable the work that will be necessary at the community level for success and impact.

We will leverage the influence of the RADx-UP program to advocate for and develop more responsive planning and design processes and more comprehensive funding mechanisms, which may include diversifying our funding sources beyond the NIH.

Why

Funding structures need to embrace a more holistic perspective that sees communities as essential partners – not just in execution but also in planning and design.

How

C8: Advocate for a redesign of funding mechanisms to be more responsive to community needs

Our strategy is to leverage our strength as an academic community partnership to encourage adjustments to current funding mechanisms that will better accommodate the challenges and constraints faced by community partners. This will allow for creativity, flexibility and human engagement that existing systems and structures inhibit.

C9: Expand capacity-building opportunities and resources available to communities

Our strategy is to broaden funding parameters in order to provide resources directly to communities to strengthen their community-engaged research infrastructure. We will train and retain the people beyond specific research projects.

C10: Cultivate new funding streams for community driven health disparities research

Our strategy is to identify, engage, or develop a wider range of funding sources that allow for greater flexibility and sustainability.

Direction D.

Bridge research and policy to drive systemic change toward health equity

Goal

We will ensure that our research is positioned to help shape the policies that shape health outcomes. This means ensuring our data is meaningful and usable and strengthening relationships with policymakers who can help interpret and champion it.

Why

Ultimately, this work needs to impact the way that people receive health care and it must contribute to greater equity in health outcomes overall.

How

D11: Strengthen integration between policy and community-driven research

Our strategy is to plan ahead to ensure that research findings are useful and usable by decision makers and to build the relationships needed to carry this strategy forward.

D12: Make health care accessible, culturally competent, and driven by community needs

Our strategy is to advocate for more affordable, patient centered health care and health information, as well as funding of services that contribute to positive health outcomes. We will ensure that care gets to patients in the way they need. We cannot do this alone; we intend to partner with those who can.